

The Spectrum of Anemia in Chronic Kidney Disease Patients in Tertiary Care Center

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Abstract:

Introduction: Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a global health issue affecting over 10% of adults and up to 50% in high-risk groups, such as the elderly and those with diabetes or HIV/AIDS. CKD often leads to anemia due to decreased erythropoietin production by the kidneys, increasing mortality and reducing quality of life.

Aims and Objective: To examine the hematological profile of CKD patients and correlate blood count measures with CKD stages in a tertiary care hospital.

Material and Methods: This cross-sectional study, conducted from January to June 2024, included adult CKD patients at various stages, excluding those with conditions causing anemia unrelated to CKD. Data were collected through patient interviews, clinical examinations, and medical records. Hematological parameters were analyzed to assess anemia type and severity, with statistical methods determining prevalence across CKD stages to guide better management strategies.

Results: Out of 256 CKD patients, 82% had normocytic normochromic anemia and 18% had microcytic hypochromic anemia, with no significant age ($p > 0.05$) or sex differences ($p > 0.05$) between the groups. Most patients were employed in the private sector (17.2%), were farmers (17.6%), housewives (20.7%), or shopkeepers (16.0%), with occupation differences being statistically significant ($p = 0.032$) but not influencing anemia type. Weakness was the most common complaint (86%), with no significant difference between anemia types ($p > 0.05$). Anemia was most prevalent in CKD stage 5 (86%), with no significant variation by anemia type across stages ($p > 0.05$). Significant differences were observed in mean MCV and MCH values between anemia groups ($p < 0.05$), and correlations of RBC count, Hb, hematocrit, MCHC, blood urea, and serum creatinine with CKD stages were also significant ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) is a prevalent global health issue, often leading to anemia, which worsens with disease severity. The most common types of anemia in CKD are normocytic normochromic (due to erythropoietin deficiency) and microcytic hypochromic (due to iron deficiency). Evaluating hemoglobin and RBC parameters in CKD patients is crucial for accurate anemia classification and appropriate treatment selection, preventing unnecessary iron overload.

Keywords: Chronic Kidney Disease, Anemia, Hematological Impairment, Erythropoietin Deficiency.

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Introduction

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a major global public health problem, [1] estimated to affect more than 10% of the general adult population and up to 50% of some high-risk subpopulations, such as the elderly, [2] those with non-communicable diseases (NCDs), including type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2D) and hypertension, and communicable diseases (CDs), including HIV/AIDS. [3]

CKD encompasses a wide range of physiological processes altered by the progressive decline in glomerular filtration rate (GFR). [4]

Haematological parameters, particularly red blood cell (RBC) indices, are most commonly affected, [5] giving rise to anaemia. Anaemia is the most common, consistent and severe of the various haematological abnormalities, and has been shown to be a very common condition in Indians. The predominant cause of anaemia in CKD is failure of the kidneys to produce enough endogenous erythropoietin, which accompanies the fall in GFR. [6] Untreated, prolonged anaemia is strongly predictive of all-cause and cardiovascular

mortality, as well as reduced quality of life and increased morbidity in patients with CKD. [5] Untreated anaemia can also accelerate the decline in renal function by causing renal haemodynamic alterations and tissue hypoxia. [7] We therefore aimed to characterize the haematological spectrum of screen-detected CKD participants, and to correlate the complete blood count measures with CKD stages in tertiary care hospital.

Material and Methods

This cross-sectional study was conducted at the Tertiary Care Center over a period of six months, from January to June 2024. The study included patients diagnosed with chronic kidney disease (CKD) at various stages, who presented to the nephrology outpatient department or were admitted to the hospital. Inclusion criteria comprised adult patients aged 18 years and above with established CKD, defined according to the Kidney Disease Improving Global Outcomes (KDIGO) guidelines. Exclusion criteria included patients with acute kidney injury, those on dialysis for less than three months, and those with other conditions causing anemia, such as hemolytic disorders, active bleeding, or recent blood transfusions.

Data collection involved detailed patient interviews, clinical examinations, and review of medical records to gather demographic information, clinical history, laboratory data, and medication use. Hemoglobin levels, hematocrit, mean corpuscular volume (MCV), mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC), iron studies, and erythropoietin levels were assessed to determine the presence and type of anemia. The severity of anemia was categorized based on hemoglobin levels, following the World Health Organization (WHO) classification. CKD stages were identified using estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) calculated by the Modification of Diet in Renal Disease (MDRD) formula.

Statistical analysis was performed using appropriate software to determine the prevalence and types of anemia across different CKD stages.

Categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages, while continuous variables were summarized as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Chi-square tests were used to compare categorical variables, and analysis of variance (ANOVA) was applied for continuous variables. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant. The study aimed to evaluate the spectrum and severity of anemia in CKD patients to inform better management strategies and improve patient outcomes.

Results

Out of 256 patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD), the majority (82%) were found to have normocytic normochromic anemia, while 18% had microcytic hypochromic anemia. The mean age of patients with microcytic anemia was 44.83 years, and for those with normocytic anemia, it was 45.31 years, indicating no statistically significant difference in the age distribution between the two groups ($p > 0.05$). Sex distribution among the anemia types showed that 64.5% of the CKD patients were male, with 58.7% of males having microcytic anemia and 65.7% having normocytic anemia. The difference in sex distribution was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

Regarding occupation, the majority of CKD patients were employed in the private sector (17.2%), followed by farmers (17.6%), housewives (20.7%), and shopkeepers (16.0%). While there was a statistically significant difference in the distribution of occupations between the anemia types ($p = 0.032$), this difference did not substantially impact the type of anemia in CKD patients. The chief complaint in majority of the CKD patients (86%) was weakness followed by fever (14%). By anemic type the complaints in both the groups were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). Only 3 patients out of 256 CKD patients had positive family history of normocytic normochromic anemia with insignificant difference statistically. Most of the patients (86%) had been complicated by anemia in fifth stage of CKD. The type of anemia had not significant difference in any stage of CKD in both the groups ($p > 0.05$).

Table 1: Distribution of Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) Stages Between Anemia Types in Patients

Stage of CKD	Microcytic Hypochromic	Normocytic Normochromic	Total	P value
3	3 (6.5%)	4 (1.9%)	7 (2.7%)	0.116
4	7 (15.2%)	21 (10.0%)	28 (10.9%)	
5	36 (78.3%)	185 (88.1%)	221 (86.3%)	

On comparing hematological parameters between two groups of anemia, mean MCV and MCH values were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). On Pearson correlation between RBC parameters with

stages of CKD, mean RBC count, Hb level, hematocrit value, MCHC, blood urea and serum creatinine level were statistically significant in different stages of CKD ($p < 0.05$).

RBC Parameters	Stage 3 (MH)	Stage 3 (NN)	Stage 4 (MH)	Stage 4 (NN)	Stage 5 (MH)	Stage 5 (NN)	P value
RBC Count (million/cumm)	2.10 ± 0.72	3.70 ± 0.11	2.15 ± 0.81	2.86 ± 0.69	2.64 ± 0.66	2.51 ± 0.66	0.702
Hb (g/dl)	6.23 ± 1.74	11.20 ± 0.16	6.54 ± 2.52	8.77 ± 2.13	7.91 ± 1.91	7.60 ± 1.96	0.564
Hematocrit (%)	19.33 ± 5.50	34.50 ± 0.57	20.27 ± 7.85	27.09 ± 6.52	24.43 ± 5.71	23.36 ± 5.91	0.630
MCV (fl)	75.23 ± 1.08	89.75 ± 5.90	69.70 ± 5.62	86.46 ± 4.92	74.94 ± 9.11	85.97 ± 6.30	<0.001
MCH (pg)	22.00 ± 1.73	28.25 ± 0.95	24.91 ± 2.10	27.25 ± 2.40	24.67 ± 2.93	27.19 ± 2.94	<0.001
MCHC (%)	29.13 ± 1.02	29.75 ± 0.50	30.88 ± 3.91	30.48 ± 1.91	32.01 ± 3.51	31.29 ± 2.87	0.323

Discussion

CKD is one of the worldwide public health issues and anemia is the most common complication of advanced CKD. [8] The prevalence of CKD in India in different communities is about 0.16% and other renal disorders is about 0.7%. [9] The recent population-based study assessed the incidence at 150-200 cases per million population per year in India. [10]

The anemia in CKD is mainly caused by insufficient production of erythropoietin by diseased kidneys. Iron deficiency, chronic inflammation, hyperparathyroidism, and blood loss may also contribute to anemia in these patients. Recombinant human erythropoietin (rHuEPO) has been used in the treatment of the anemia of CKD since 1986. [11] Our study evaluated the spectrum profile of anemia in patients of Chronic Kidney Disease presenting at a tertiary care center.

In our study out of 256 CKD patients, 46 patients (18%) had microcytic hypochromic anemia while majority of the patients (82%) had normocytic normochromic anemia. Most of the patients in our study had normocytic normochromic anemia (82%) on peripheral blood smear examination, followed by microcytic hypochromic anemia (18%). The predominantly normocytic normochromic picture on PBF is because of the absolute deficiency of Erythropoietin (Epo) with progressive renal dysfunction. Majority of the previous studies have shown similar findings with regards to morphological picture of Anemia. Arun et al. [12] showed in their study that all though most of the anemia was of the normocytic type, nearly a third of the patients had microcytic hypochromic and a mixed type of anemia. Those with a microcytic hypochromic picture correlated with a severe degree of anemia. [12,13] Akinsola et al. [13] showed in his study that red cell morphology was variable but the majority of patients showed a normocytic, normochromic blood film.

Talwar et al. [14] showed a higher incidence of microcytic hypochromic anemia compared to our

study population. Lesser incidence in our study population could be explained by the fact that majority of patients in advanced stages of renal failure receive oral or parenteral iron as prophylactic even before evaluation for iron deficiency. In the study by Arun et al., [12] 25% of cases showed features of both normocytic normochromic anemia and microcytic hypochromic anemia, but iron deficiency was associated with only subset of cases.

A study by Vikrant et al. [15] found that the anemia was normocytic in 65.4%, microcytic in 14.2%, and macrocytic in 20.4%. Normocytic normochromic anemia in renal failure patients is mainly hypoproliferative anemia due to EPO deficiency leading to bone marrow suppression and peripheral destruction.

In our study mean age of the patients was 44.83 in patients diagnosed with microcytic anemia while in normochromic anemia mean age was 45.31 with non-significance difference statistically ($p > 0.05$) According to the meta-analysis by Shiferaw et al. [16], the pooled effects of four studies indicated that those over 50 years of age were 62% more likely to develop anemia compared to those less than 50 years old, although this association was not statistically significant. Another study by Vikrant et al. [15] reported around 55% patients were male and 45% were female. Mean age of the patients was 55.5 years in this study. [15] A study by Shastry et al. [17] found that the mean age of presentation was 52 ± 14 years with male-to-female ratio was 4.3:1.

In our study majority of the male patients (64.5%) with CKD were developed anemias. By anemic type the difference in sex distribution among CKD patients was not statistically significant. ($p > 0.05$) The results are different from the systemic review by Shiferaw et al. [16] in 2020, females were 36% more likely to develop anemia in patients with CKD than male patients. The predominant impact of anemia in female sex CKD patients is supported by previous studies conducted in Korea [18], Australia [19], London [20], and New York

[21]. This would suggest that female patients had lower Hb concentrations than male patients, which likely explains why females had greater risk of developing anemia. [22] Epidemiological data by the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey 3 and the Kidney Early Evaluation Program show an increase in the prevalence of anemia in individuals aged >61 years in the presence of Stage 3 CKD or higher. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the prevalence of anemia is 43% in patients with CKD.

The chief complaint in majority of the CKD patients (86%) was weakness followed by fever (14%). By anemic type the complaints in both the groups were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

Majority of the patients with CKD were associated with profession of private sector employment, farmer, housewife and shopkeeper. Only 3 out of 256 CKD patients had positive family history of normocytic normochromic anemia with insignificant difference statistically. This nullifies the impact of positive family history and occupation upon occurrence of particular type anemia in CKD patients. Non-significant impact of occupation in our study is supported by Hussain et al. [23] found no significant difference between the anemic and nonanemic patients regarding sex, marital status, family history education, occupation, substance use, family income, and co-morbidities.

In present study those patients with advanced stage of CKD (stage 5) had a significant association with a anemia, which has been previously reported in studies conducted in Australia¹⁹, Korea [20], New York [22] and Florida²⁴. This association is likely explained by the deterioration of renal function being accompanied by a reduction in erythropoietin production by the kidneys, and the loss of erythropoietin results in decreased red blood cell production that increases the risk of anemia development. [25,26] Shiferaw et al. [16] evaluated the pooled effects of seven studies showed that stage 5 CKD patients' were 13 times more likely to develop anemia than patients with stage 1 CKD.

In our study we found that mean RBC count, Hb level, hematocrit value, MCHC, blood urea and serum creatinine level were statistically significant in different stages of CKD ($p < 0.05$). Seven (2.7%) patients were CKD Stage 3, 28 (10.9%) patients CKD Stage 4, and 221 (86.3%) patients CKD Stage 5. The mean hemoglobin was 8.2 ± 2.2 g/dL. There was a progressive fall in hemoglobin with increasing severity of CKD, and in CKD Stage 3, 4, and 5 the mean hemoglobin was 9.1, 7.9, and 7.2 g/dL, respectively ($P = 0.001$). A study by Vikrant et al.¹⁵ demonstrated that around seventy-two (12.3%) patients were CKD Stage 3, 193 (33%) patients CKD Stage 4, and 319 (54.6%) patients CKD Stage 5. The mean hemoglobin was 9.2 ± 2.2

g/dL. There was a progressive fall in hemoglobin with increasing severity of CKD, and in CKD Stage 3, 4, and 5 the mean hemoglobin was 10 ± 2.2 , 9.4 ± 2.1 , and 8.4 ± 1.9 g/dL, respectively.¹⁵

Our study demonstrated no impact of severity of CKD upon RBC count. A study by Shastry et al. reported that the low RBC count in the study population which worsened as the renal function deteriorated. Only those cases who received EPO showed normal RBC counts along with normal Hb and PCV. A statistically significant correlation was observed in our study between the severity of anemia and the stage of renal failure, suggesting that severe anemia is more likely to be associated with Stage V renal failure. These findings agree with the studies by Talwar et al., [14] and Singh et al., [27] which also showed low RBC counts, Hb, and hematocrit values associated with CKD patients

A study by Shastry et al.¹⁷ found that the mean RBC count was $3.29 \pm 0.79 \times 10^6/\mu\text{l}$, and a significant fall was noticed as the stage of CKD progressed. 74% and 60% of patients with Stage 4 and 5 CKD, respectively, showed Hb of < 10 g/dl. Correlation of MCV, MCH, and MCHC values with stages of CKD was statistically not significant. In the study by Alghythan and Alsaed [28], RBC count, Hb, and PCV levels, although within normal range, were significantly lower when compared with the control population. A study conducted by Shittu et al. [29] showed comparatively lower MCV and MCH values, but it was not statistically significant because the control population also showed similar values and did not show significant differences in RBC indices in different stages of renal failure. Similarly, in our study, patients in different stages of renal failure did not show significant changes in RBC indices. In general stage 5 CKD, being male were found to be significantly associated with anemia of chronic kidney disease. Therefore, situation-based interventions and country context-specific preventive strategies should be developed to reduce the risk factors of anemia in this patient group.

Conclusion

Chronic Kidney Disease is a major health care problem worldwide, with a global prevalence of 8-16%. Chronic Kidney Disease leads to a wide range of systemic derangements. Anemia is a very common manifestation among patients of CKD. As the renal dysfunction increases in severity, there is proportional increase in prevalence and severity of haematological impairment. Anemia is a leading cause of morbidity in patients with CKD and it worsens with the stage of the disease. The most common type of anemia is normocytic normochromic anemia due to EPO deficiency and microcytic hypochromic anemia due to iron

deficiency. Evaluation of Hb and RBC parameters in patients with CKD helps in classifying the type of anemia and aids in choosing the correct treatment modalities and avoids unnecessary iron overload in the patients.

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